

WHAT WE'LL SEE DOWN

TWO PATHWAYS

TO ZERO EMISSIONS FROM BUILDINGS

Annex D:

Indigenous Community District Energy Costing Analysis

June 2025

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The logo for the Government of Canada, featuring the word "Canada" in a large, black, serif font. A small red maple leaf is positioned above the letter "a". To the left of the word "Canada" is a vertical black line.

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MEMORANDUM

TO	Michael Wiggin - Boltzmann Institute
FROM	Gary Saskiw - FVB Energy (FVB)
DATE	2025-05-16
DISTRIBUTION	FVB - Internal
SUBJECT	Community District Energy Costing Analysis Memorandum

SUMMARY

FVB has been retained to provide this costing analysis that reflects a Oujé-Bougoumou district heating (DH) system based on current technologies, best practices, and lessons learned over the last 30 years from the Oujé-Bougoumou DH system. This includes separate biomass heating plants & peaking/back-up heating plants, industrial-grade biomass heating systems, and PEX buried piping with buried isolation valves for each customer building connection and substations (ETs) with isolating heat exchangers (indirect) connections and improved flow/temperature controls.

The buildings described within assumes ~175 single-family residences, and ~30 public buildings of various building types and sizes typical for a community of this size.

This memo provides a marginal comparison between building self-generation concepts and a district heating system that serves the entire community. The building self-generation concepts include for heat generation equipment and are based on technologies that require fuel oil and/or electricity. The district heating system concept includes for biomass boilers for baseload capacity and fuel-oil boilers for peaking & back-up capacity.

This comparison accounts for the building self-generation costs that is avoided with connection to a district heating system compared against the district heating costs associated with providing full thermal heating services.

The capital + annual cost comparison and corresponding simple payback result is shown in the following table:

Description	Building Self-Generation	District Heating System	Marginal Comparison
Marginal Capital Cost [A]	\$8.9 million	\$37.6 million	\$28.7 million
Marginal Annual Cost [B]	\$2.5 million	\$1.2 million	-\$1.3 million
Simple Payback [A/B]			22 yrs

As shown above, the district heating system capital cost is estimated to be ~4 times the building self-generation cost. However, the district heating system annual costs are estimated to be ~½ the building self-generation annual costs – driven largely by utility cost decreases.

Additionally, the district heating system would reduce the community's greenhouse gas footprint by ~85% and has the potential to reduce the community's peak electricity demand by ~3 MVA.

Disclaimer

The information and data contained herein represent FVB's best professional judgment in light of the knowledge and information available to FVB at the time of preparation. FVB does not accept any responsibility whatsoever or howsoever arising, whether by reason of inaccuracy or negligence on its part or otherwise, for any loss, damage, cost, or expense suffered as a result of reliance by any third party on the contents of this memorandum.

The analysis provided is general in nature and intended to convey opinions & observations of FVB based on our extensive experience with district energy systems and cannot be relied upon by any person other than the client.

Issue	Reviewed By	Date
Draft Issue	B. Skagestad, P.Eng.	April 24, 2025
Final Issue	B. Skagestad, P.Eng.	May 16, 2025

1 INTRODUCTION

FVB was asked to prepare this memo that compares a biomass-based district heating system against individual building self-generation of heat using electricity / fuel oil energy sources. The concepts consider heating service for an entire community and are generally based on the Oujé-Bougoumou district heating system.

The following are key results that are provided in this memo:

- Estimates of community building peak heating demand and annual thermal energy requirements.
- Definition of building self-generation concepts, and district heating system concepts.
- Estimate building avoided capital costs and district heating capital costs for each major component.
- Estimate building self-generation + district heating annual utility costs, operation & maintenance costs, and greenhouse gas (GHG) footprint.
- Marginal comparison between building heating self-generation + district heating system, including simple payback and GHG reduction.
- Sensitivity analysis of key project variables.
- Lessons learned and key capacity building issues of the Oujé-Bougoumou district heating system.

This memo is intended to support the larger district energy pathway and Indigenous community feasibility study being prepared by FVB for the Boltzmann's Institute.

1.1 RELATIVE ACCURACY

The evaluation provided is general in nature and intended to convey opinions & observations of FVB based on our experience with district energy system infrastructure. The accuracy of the presented results should be considered as preliminary only.

1.2 KEY PROJECT CONSIDERATIONS

The key characteristics of the community are assumed as follows:

- Community buildings that are considered typical for an Indigenous community of ~800 people:
 - ~175 single-family residences
 - ~30 public buildings
- The community is accessible by road year-round and is located within an hour of a major community.
- Heat is generated using biomass (wood chips), heating fuel oil, and/or grid electricity.
- The community can provide local labour support and has access to major construction equipment.
- No challenging geotechnical conditions are identified in the region that may impact the buried installation (i.e., permafrost, bedrock, etc.).
- Minimal reinstatement requirements (i.e., no enhanced landscaping, road paving, major crossings, etc.).
- No major additional system requirements (i.e., enhanced building architectural, enhanced noise / emission mitigation requirements, etc.).

2 BUILDING SELF GENERATION

This section describes the core assumptions related to building types within the community and their peak thermal and annual thermal energy requirements, and assumptions related to self-generation heating concepts (where the community buildings generate their own heating energy services (i.e., 'business-as-usual', or BAU).

2.1 BUILDING PEAK DEMAND & ANNUAL THERMAL ENERGY

The estimated peak demand and annual thermal energy requirements for the site at key stages of project buildout are shown in the following table:

Table 1: Estimated Building Peak Demand & Annual Thermal Energy Requirement

Description	Single-Family Residences	Public Buildings	Total
No of Buildings	175	30	205
Peak Heating Demand	2,000 kW _t	1,950 kW _t	3,950 kW_t
Annual Thermal Energy	5,000 MWh _t	5,000 MWh _t	10,000 MWh_t

The 205 buildings within the community have an assumed combined undiversified peak heating demand of ~3,950 kW_t and annual thermal energy of 10,000 MWh_t.

2.2 BUILDING SELF-GENERATION CONCEPT

This memo assumes the buildings have installed the following heating equipment for each building types:

- Single-Family Residences
 - Electric furnaces + heat recovery ventilators (HRVs).
 - Electric residential domestic hot water (DHW) heaters.
- Public Buildings
 - Fuel oil boilers that serve hydronic terminal units throughout the building (air handling systems, unit heaters, radiant systems, etc.).¹
 - Electric residential domestic hot water (DHW) heaters.

¹ Smaller public buildings may have electric / fuel oil furnaces + heat recovery ventilators (HRVs).

3 DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEM

This section describes the proposed district heating system concept that is further evaluated in this memo.

3.1 DISTRICT HEATING PEAK LOAD & ANNUAL THERMAL ENERGY

This memo assumes a system diversification of ~85% for heating, and an average annual district heating system thermal inefficiency of ~12%. This results in a district heating system with a peak heating load of ~3,300 kW_t and annual thermal energy production requirement of ~11,200 MWh_t.

3.2 DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEM COMPONENTS

There are four distinct components of the proposed district heating system: the biomass heating plant that provides baseload heating production, the peaking/back-up heating plant that provides peak heating production and capacity redundancy, the distribution piping system that carries the hot water from the heating plants to community buildings, and the customer building equipment to interface with building systems.

3.2.1 BIOMASS HEATING PLANT

The biomass 'heating plant' is the central point of thermal energy production for the district heating system. This study assumes the use of biomass wood chips with an average moisture content of 45%. The biomass fuel feedstock is delivered to a fuel bin with walking floor, then conveyed to two (2) industrial-grade, packaged biomass heating systems with a combined nominal capacity of ~2,500 kW_t. The biomass heating plant is estimated to provide ~95% of the annual thermal energy and ~75% of the peak district heating load.

3.2.2 PEAKING / BACK-UP HEATING PLANT

The peaking + back-up 'heating plant' includes additional conventional heating capacity to provide peak heating production and system equipment redundancy. This memo assumes the installation of two (2) industrial-grade, packaged fuel oil boiler systems with a combined nominal capacity of ~3,000 kW_t.

3.2.3 DISTRIBUTION PIPING SYSTEM

The distribution piping system (DPS) is a closed-loop network of ~12,500 trench metres (tm) of piping² that supplies heated water to the community buildings. Pre-insulated, cross-linked polyethylene (PEX) piping is installed in shallow trenches with sand bedding, native fill, and gravel reinstatement. Each branch connection includes buried isolation valves and transitions to steel or copper piping within the buildings.

3.2.4 BUILDING DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEM INTERFACES

Each building connection comprises of interfaces between the district heating system and customer building space heating and domestic hot water systems. This includes for items such as DHW heat exchangers + storage tanks, pumps, controls and instrumentation, thermal energy meter, isolation valves, and associated accessories and piping. Single-family residences + some smaller public buildings are assumed to have fan coils + heat recovery units (HRVs), while the larger public buildings would have a more traditional heat exchanger interface + connection to the building's hydronic HVAC system.

² Note, the DPS includes an additional 10-15% of pipe length for looping to help with flow problems caused by low delta T.

4 ANALYSIS RESULTS

This section defines the indicative capital costs, annual costs, and greenhouse gas footprint of both the building self-generation concept and the district heating system.

4.1 CAPITAL COSTS

The avoided capital costs associated with building self-generation, and capital costs associated with the district heating system is shown in the following table³:

Table 2: Capital Cost Estimate Results

Description	Building Self Generation	District Heating System	Marginal Comparison
Building Self Generation			
Single Family Residences	\$3.3 million	-	<i>-\$3.3 million</i>
Public Buildings	\$5.6 million	-	<i>-\$5.6 million</i>
Heating Plant			
Biomass Heating Plant	-	\$11.3 million	<i>\$11.3 million</i>
Peaking / Back-up Plant	-	\$3.8 million	<i>\$3.8 million</i>
Distribution Piping System	-	\$16.3 million	<i>\$16.3 million</i>
Building DH Interfaces			
Single Family Residences	-	\$3.8 million	<i>\$3.8 million</i>
Public Buildings	-	\$2.4 million	<i>\$2.4 million</i>
Total Capital Cost	\$8.9 million	\$37.6 million	<i>\$28.7 million</i>

As shown in the table above, district heating system has a significantly higher capital cost over building self-generation. Most of the district heating capital is associated with the low-carbon technology (biomass heating plant), and the distribution piping system.

As well, it should also be noted that there is a premium for building district heating interfaces for the single-family residences over building heating self-generation. However, the building district heating interfaces are significantly lower for building district heating interfaces for the public buildings over building heating self-generation.

Note, it is estimated that the district heating system would avoid ~3 MVA of peak electrical demand within the community. Costs associated with additional electricity generation, transmission lines, local electrical distribution, and primary electric service are not included in the building self-generation costs.

Please refer to Appendix A for the resulting unit costs that are calculated from the above capital cost estimates.

³ The cost estimates are preliminary and based on limited information and subsequently have wide accuracy ranges.

4.2 ANNUAL COSTS

The following table summarizes the annual costs estimates for the building self-generation and district heating system concepts:

Table 3: Annual Cost Estimate Results

Description	Building Self Generation	District Heating System	Marginal Comparison
Utilities			
Grid Electricity	\$540 k	\$50 k	-\$490 k
Biomass	-	\$350 k	\$350 k
Fuel Oil	\$1,300 k	\$100 k	-\$1,200 k
Maintenance Costs	\$450 k	\$340 k	-\$110 k
Operating Labour & Supervision	\$170 k	\$330 k	\$160 k
Total Annual Cost	\$2,460 k	\$1,170 k	-\$1,290 k

As shown, the annual costs associated with the district heating system is ~½ of building self-generation. This is largely attributed to a reduction in utility costs.

Note that building self-generation has a lower operation + maintenance cost. The trade-off is that this typically results in a lower average annual system thermal efficiency, and a lower equipment service life.

Please refer to Appendix B for assumptions utilized for the annual costs.

4.3 SIMPLE PAYBACK

A simple payback for the district heating system can be calculated from the marginal capital cost and marginal annual costs shown in the sections above.

The following table summarizes the simple payback for the district heating system:

Table 4: District Heating System Simple Payback Results

Description	Results
Marginal Capital Cost [A]	\$28.7 million
Marginal Annual Cost [B]	-\$1.29 million
Simple Payback [A/B]	22 yrs

As shown, the district heating system has a simple payback of ~22 years. This can be reduced with grant funding to reduce project capital, or by finding synergies within the community to reduce operating labour costs. The fuel cost difference between biomass and oil are also a major factor in terms of simple paybacks.

4.4 GREENHOUSE GAS FOOTPRINT

The following table summarizes the greenhouse gas (GHG) footprint estimates for the building self-generation and district heating system concepts:

Table 5: Annual Greenhouse Gas Footprint Estimate Results

Description	Building Self Generation	District Heating System	Marginal Comparison
Grid Electricity ⁴	10 tCO _{2e}	0 tCO _{2e}	-10 tCO _{2e}
Biomass	-	-	-
Fuel Oil	2,060 tCO _{2e}	180 tCO _{2e}	-1,880 tCO _{2e}
Total GHG Footprint	2,070 tCO_{2e}	180 tCO_{2e}	-1,890 tCO_{2e} -90%

As shown, the district heating system would result in ~90% reduction in the community GHG footprint.

Please refer to Appendix B for assumptions utilized for the greenhouse gas intensities.

⁴ Note, the GHG footprint estimates are rounded to the nearest 10 tonnes of carbon dioxide equivalent. There can be expected to be less than 5 tonnes of CO_{2e} associated with electricity usage for the district heating system.

5 ANALYSIS SENSITIVITIES

This memo considers additional sensitivities for major items that would impact the simple payback of the district heating system project.

The following sensitivity⁵ scenarios were considered:

- Biomass Fuel Feedstock:
 - Base Case: Wood chips with 40% moisture content at \$80 per wet tonnes delivered
 - Wood Pellets: Wood pellets with 6% moisture content at ~\$120 per wet tonnes delivered
 - Wood Chips: Wood chips with 65% moisture content at \$80 per wet tonnes delivered

- Fuel Oil Utility Cost:
 - Base Case: Building Self-Generation: Delivered cost of \$1.75 per Litre
District Heating System: Delivered cost of \$1.60 per Litre
 - High Cost: Building Self-Generation: Delivered cost of \$2.65 per Litre
District Heating System: Delivered cost of \$2.40 per Litre
 - Low Cost: Building Self-Generation: Delivered cost of \$0.90 per Litre
District Heating System: Delivered cost of \$0.80 per Litre

- Community Thermal Requirements
 - Base Case: Peak heating load of ~3,300 kW_t
Annual thermal energy production of ~11,200 MWh_t
 - High Building Density: Peak heating load of ~5,000 kW_t
Annual thermal energy production of ~16,800 MWh_t
 - Low Building Density: Peak heating load of ~1,700 kW_t
Annual thermal energy production of ~5,600 MWh_t

⁵ High/Low sensitives for Fuel Oil and Building Load Density are based on +50%/-50%.

The following table summarizes the simple payback results for the additional sensitivity scenarios:

Table 6: Project Sensitivity Simple Payback Results

Description	Simple Payback
Base Case	22 yrs
Biomass Fuel Feedstock	
Wood Pellets (Premium Quality)	21 yrs
Wood Chips (Poor Quality)	35 yrs
Fuel Oil Utility Cost	
High Cost	15 yrs
Low Cost	41 yrs
Community Thermal Requirements	
High Building Load Density	16 yrs
Low Building Load Density	54 yrs

As shown in the table above, the wood pellet premium quality biomass fuel feedstock has negligible impact to the simple payback results for the district heating system. However, a poor-quality biomass fuel feedstock resulted in a significantly longer simple payback period.

Both the fuel oil utility costs and the building load density within the community resulted in a large impact to the simple payback results.

6 LESSONS LEARNED + KEY CAPACITY BUILDING ISSUES

The following are a few lessons learned, and key capacity building issues based on FVB’s experience in Oujé:

Description	Concern	Recommendation
Building System Design	Significant heating performance challenges due to incompatibilities between the high delta T DH system and the low delta T design of some building heating systems.	Establish firm DH system connection guidelines and a design peer review process for new building customers or major renovations in existing building heating systems.
Building DHW	Ongoing problems with instantaneous DHW configurations with frequent heat exchanger leaks and poor flow and temperature controls.	Configure DHW systems with some storage, in a charging configuration, in combination with motorized DH control valves and domestic side circulation pump.
Building Interface Design	Interactivity and cross-contamination / leaking potential between the DH system and direct-connect building hydronic heating systems reducing DH system performance and reliability.	Enhance customer building connection and substation (ETSS) design with isolating heat exchangers (indirect) ⁶ connections and improved flow/temperature controls. This includes using control valves that can handle high(er) differential pressures (dP) and/or the use of dP valves.
Distribution Piping System Leaks / Installation	Water treatment and leaking problems caused by distribution piping corrosion, in combination with challenges associated with welding (including access to certified welders).	Implement PEX piping as much as possible. Even with an all PEX piping system, water treatment remains a priority to protect other parts of the system (including in-building systems).
Biomass Fire Hazard	Generally elevated fire risks associated with the use of biomass technologies.	Maintain separate biomass heating plants & peaking/back-up heating plants.
Biomass Fuel Storage	Foreign matter including ice, sand, grit and water ingress being introduced into the biomass feedstock after delivery.	Develop a more robust biomass fuel transfer and storage enclosure design, including proper ventilation & heating.

⁶ Fan Coil Units or in-floor radiant hydronic heating (with HEXs) in single family homes.

Description	Concern	Recommendation
Biomass Heating System	Operational limitations for switching fuel feedstocks and equipment serviceability/reliability with a commercial-grade biomass heating system.	Install a more industrial-grade biomass heating system for increased reliability, longevity, and fuel feedstock flexibility.
Biomass Fuel Quality	Significant variations in fuel feedstock size, quality, and moisture content negatively impacting major equipment performance and condition.	Conduct a fuel feedstock assessment study and/or procure a reliable supply of consistent higher-grade fuel (e.g., wood pellets).
O&M Program	The current plant operating and maintenance program (generally) follows more of a reactive approach, addressing problems as they arise.	Establish operating procedures and reporting requirements for the plant operators, including standard operating procedures (SOPs), key performance indicators (KPIs), preventative maintenance procedures, etc.
Staff Turnover	Retaining local staff trained and committed to operating and maintaining the system on a consistent basis.	Implement more training opportunities for operation staff growth, and, as importantly, identify key staff to take ownership and pride of the district heating system.
Staff Training	Staff have (generally) been trained on the job, in response to challenges arising in the system. More recently, some training by 3 rd party has been initiated.	Provide ongoing training, including formal training at technical colleges or institutes with the goal of obtaining operator licenses (e.g. Class 4).
Political Risk	Changes in local council may present interest in alternative solutions to the current DH system (e.g., geo-exchange, electrification) and challenge opportunities for future investment and system growth.	Continually inform and educate councillors and other decision makers on the positive benefits and impacts of the existing DH system in comparison to buildings self-generation (aka status quo).

APPENDIX A UNIT COST RESULTS

The following table summarizes the resulting unit costs from the capital cost estimates shown above:

Table 7: Unit Cost Results

Description	Qty	Unit Cost
Building Self Generation		
Single Family Residences	175	\$19,000 / bldg.
Public Buildings	30	\$185,000 / bldg.
Biomass Heating Plant	2,500 kW _t	\$4,500 / kW _t
Peaking / Back-up Plant	3,000 kW _t	\$1,250 / kW _t
Distribution Piping System	12,500 tm	\$1,300 / tm
Building Connection		
Single Family Residences	175	\$21,500 / bldg.
Public Buildings	30	\$80,000 / bldg.

APPENDIX B ANALYSIS ASSUMPTIONS

The analysis presented in this memo is based on the following assumptions:

- General
 - All values are presented in 2025 Q1 Canadian Dollars and exclude taxes.

- Utility Rates
 - Blended Grid Electricity Cost⁷: \$0.10 per kWh_e for Building Self-Generation
\$0.10 per kWh_e for the District Heating System
 - Biomass Delivered Cost: \$80 per wet tonnes delivered.
 - Fuel Oil Delivered Cost⁸: \$1.75 per litre for Building Self-Generation
\$1.60 per litre for the District Heating System

- Major Equipment Average Annual Thermal Efficiencies
 - Electric Boilers / Furnaces: 95%
 - Fuel Oil Boiler: 65% Bldg. Self-Generation / 80% District Heating
 - Biomass Heating System: ~73%

- District Heating System Annual Costs
 - The annual costs associated with the district heating system concept are estimated using in-house data of similar systems or published data from recognized sources.
 - Includes an allocation of 4 full-time equivalent operation labour for operating and performing general maintenance and housekeeping duties.
 - Includes for major equipment and infrastructure maintenance for the heating plant systems, distribution piping, and customer building interfaces, and assumes the use of a sinking fund for major equipment replacement.

- Greenhouse Gas Emission Intensities⁹:
 - Fuel Oil: 2.76 kg CO_{2e} / Litre
 - Biomass: 0.0 kg CO_{2e} / wet tonnes
 - Electricity: 1.7 kg CO_{2e} / MWh_e

⁷ Blended electricity rate is estimated via Hydro Quebec's Rate D electricity rate schedule; effective April 1, 2025. Note that other rate structure options exist, and it appears the Hydro Quebec may be considering time-of-use rates, and demand charges to incentivize a reduction of electricity usage. If adopted, this would improve the simple payback of the District Heating System.

⁸ Annual average fuel oil rates are estimated from Table 18-10-0001-01 monthly average retail values for Quebec published by Statistics Canada.

⁹ GHG Emission Intensity factors are estimated from values published by the Government of Canada: Emission factors Version 2.0, effective May 2024.

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